

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH STORYTELLING

Ismailov Anvar Rustamovich

PhD, Associate professor of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Language

Abdiraupova Dilrabo Asror qizi

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Language

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7336499>

Abstract. *This article is about teaching English more fastly, effectively and also more interestingly though storytelling. In the continue, you can see the methods for teaching and learning English well and easily by telling stories, as well as the beneficial aspects of the method.*

Keywords: *effectively, beneficial aspects, socioemotional and cognitive skills, fairy tales, cultural knowledge, memorizing new vocabularies, imagination.*

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЧЕРЕЗ РАССКАЗЫВАНИЕ ИСТОРИЙ

Аннотация. *Эта статья посвящена более быстро, эффективно и интересному обучению английскому языку с помощью рассказывания историй. В продолжении вы можете увидеть методы преподавания и изучения английского языка хорошо и легко, рассказывая истории, а также полезные аспекты метода.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, полезные аспекты, социально-эмоциональные и когнитивные навыки, сказки, культурные знания, запоминание новой лексики, воображение.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern life, we can find any type of ways that connected to English teaching methods, for instance: singing songs, playing games, memorizing new vocabularies, watching movies and also telling stories and fairytales and others. Additionally, by telling stories in the ESL classroom, we're not only working on language skills — like vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation — we're developing imagination, creativity, and socioemotional and cognitive skills as well. We can also positively affect students' behavior and manners using this powerful tool.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Here are six classroom benefits of this amazing practice that will encourage you to use storytelling more often in your ESL classroom.

1. **Stories enhance listening skills.**

Every time we make the lesson interesting by telling stories, we unknowingly develop their listening and thinking skills and during the lesson, we also memorize new words from fairy tales, which will be quite beneficial for their in the future.

2. **They kindle creativity and imagination.**

Fairy tales encourage children to think in a new way, when they hear a fairy tale, they relive unfamiliar events in their brains at that time and imagine themselves everywhere in the mountains, fields, beaches, palaces. at this time, anything can happen in their imagination, and they also create negative and positive characters in themselves depending on their thinking.

3. **Stories boost student interest in reading.**

If we read or tell half the story of the fairy tale to them during the lesson, they will open and read the book with interest at home, because we have made them interested in the world of

imagination, and it is also for them to read. increases and improves interest. through reading, they build their self-image and memory. Developing this habit in childhood encourages kids to learn about and pursue topics of interest throughout their lives and to become more aware of other cultures and beliefs.

RESULTS

Developing this habit in childhood encourages kids to learn about and pursue topics of interest throughout their lives and to become more aware of other cultures and beliefs. People with cultural knowledge tend to be more empathic as well.

STORY LENGTH:

Look for a single, clearly defined theme, a well-developed sequential plot, a consistent style, standardized characterisation (except perhaps for the protagonist), conflict resolution, dramatic appeal, unity, interesting subject matter, and strong emotional content. Avoid stories with long explanations or descriptions, flashbacks, subplots, and other literary devices that break the flow of a story. Choose stories with positive values that implicitly express joy, compassion, humour, resourcefulness, and other positive aspects of human nature. On the other hand, experts tell us not to be excessively concerned about violence, fear, anger, hatred, lying, etc., in stories. “The point is that all children experience hostility, frustration, anger and fear. They need outlets for these feelings, just as adults do. A folktale may be able to provide just the kind of harmless release children need”.

DISCUSSION

Storytelling and the curriculum

There are three main dimensions in which stories can add to learning in the whole school curriculum:

1. Stories can be used to reinforce conceptual development in children (for example, colour, size, shape, time, cause and effect, and so on).
2. Stories are means of developing learning. This major category covers:
 - Reinforcing thinking strategies (for example, comparing, classifying, predicting, problem-solving, hypothesizing, planning, and so on).
 - Developing strategies for learning English (for example, guessing the meaning of new words, training the memory, self-testing, and so on).
 - Developing study skills (for example, making, understanding and interpreting charts and graphs, making and learning to use dictionaries, organizing work, and so on).
3. Carefully selected stories can also be used to develop other subjects in the Curriculum, in particular:
 - Mathematics telling the time, numbers: counting and quantity, measuring
 - Science the life-cycle of insects, animals, outer space, how seeds grow
 - History prehistoric animals, understanding chronology / the passing of
 - Geography and the Environment shopping and shops in the local area, neighbourhood parks, sports and games, using a map, using the atlas, the weather and climates around the world, cultural studies
 - Art and Craft drawing, making masks, hats, cards, clocks etc., making collages, making puppets
 - Music and Drama singing songs, playing instruments, role play, miming.

CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, storytelling is learned slowly over a long time, but the novice and the expert storyteller can both experience success on different levels. A storyteller eventually makes a personal collection of stories for various occasions and purposes. Storytelling is a folk-art which can't be manipulated, intellectualised, or mass-produced. Its magic is unique. The storyteller is always a teacher, and the teacher is always a storyteller. All teaching methods and suggestions in this article may be adapted to different grade and proficiency levels depending upon the type of literature chosen.

REFERENCES

1. <https://bridge.edu/tefl/blog/storytelling-for-young-learners-in-esl-classroom/>
2. Russel L. David. 2005, 38. Literature For Children.
3. Mr. sc. Mauro Dujmovic. Storytelling as a method of EFL teaching
4. Russel L. David. 2005, 165